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Review Article

COVID-19 A NEW PANDEMIC

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Abstract:

On 11 march WHO called covid-19 a pandemic because, the disease first reported in wuhan china was now spreading to many countries of the world. A pneumonia like disease first reported in December 2019 in wuhan province in china later on investigated and called as covid-19 because the causative organism is a novel corona virus having similarities with SARS-coV AND MERS-coV, till now (16th march 2020) WHO reported 164837 confirmed cases in 146 countries and 6470 deaths from COVID-19.

In this mini review we are discussing what we know till now, a brief introduction of this novel corona virus and the disease(COVID-19) caused by this virus, its general features, its genomic structure, mode of transmission, clinical features, prevention and treatment .

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INTRODUCTION:

After the outbreaks of severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) in 2002/2003 and middle east respiratory syndrome (MERS) in 2012 a new pandemic called covid-19 started in china is now rapidly spreading to involve other countries of the world.

The disease was first reported in china in December 2019 where many patients of pneumonia like disease were admitted to the hospitals in Wuhan city of china¹. The causative organism for this disease was investigated and identified as novel coronavirus². World Health Organization (WHO) temporarily named this virus as 2019 novel corona virus (2019-nCoV) on January 12 2020 because it was identified first time in humans. The disease (pneumonia type) caused by 2019-nCoV is named as COVID-19 by WHO. Later on the virus was renamed by The International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses and named as severe acute respiratory virus-2 (SARS-CoV-2)¹⁵.

Coronaviruses are large family of viruses that can cause disease to many systems of human body. There are many types of coronaviruses causing diseases in human These viruses can infect respiratory system, gastrointestinal system, central nervous system in human body and also infect livestock, birds, mouse, bat and other wild animals³⁻⁴. The disease cause by this new corona virus (COVID-19) may manifest as asymptomatic or mild to severe pneumonia. The novel coronavirus shows similarities in its genetic makeup with SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV⁵. In its initial days COVID-19 outbreak cause significant mortality and morbidity in china as compared to the rest of world¹. As its similarities with MERS-CoV in its genomic structures and in epidemiological features it is possible that animal-human and human-human transmission may occur in COVID-19⁶⁻⁸. As the outbreaks of SARS and MERS demonstrated^{7,8}.

Despite being declared epidemic by WHO the the number of infected patients increasing day by day until now (16th march 2020) the number of infected patients as reported by WHO are 164837 cases involving 146 countries with 6470 deaths. It is important to understand the mode of spread, signs and symptoms and to adopt special precautionary measures by general population and for health authorities it's important to contain this novel coronavirus and to develop effective therapies and vaccines against these viruses as it is and can be a severe threat to global health.

This mini review will be useful in understanding general features of this new coronavirus its genome, mode of transmission, clinical

presentation, prevention and treatment which we know until know.

MORPHOLOGY AND GENOM OF CORONAVIRUSES

The family of coronaviruses share similarity in their morphology and genome structure to one another. The common features of their structures are, they are spherical or pleomorphic, enveloped, 150-160nm in size with a single stranded RNA, nucleoprotein, capsid, matrix and s protein. Among the important proteins of coronaviruses are spike glycoprotein (S), membrane protein (M) and nucleocapsid protein (N)⁹. The new coronavirus is having structural similarities with SARS-CoV but It differs in a way that it contains an additional protein which is actually a glycoprotein containing acetyl esterase^{9,10}. Genom similarity of covid-19 virus is more with MERS-CoV than SARS-CoV¹⁰. Spike protein (S) is having two subunits, virus enter to host cell through the aid of one of subunit binding directly to host cell. It is reported in studies that human receptor for covid-19 virus attachment is possibly ACE2 receptors.

MODE OF TRANSMISSION & CLINICAL FEATURES OF COVID-19

Coronaviruses are mainly zoonotic. After the outbreaks of SARS and MERS studies suggested that SARS-CoV was transmitted from civet cats to human and MERS-CoV from dromedary camels¹³. Looking to the facts that Covid-19 virus is having similarity in many features to SARS-CoV and that early cases infected from covid-19 virus was all related to a seafood market in Wuhan china studies suggest that is maybe possible that animal is involved in transmitting the covid-19 to humans but its not confirmed yet¹⁴.

According to WHO reports (till now) human to human transmission of covid-19 is through is by contact, droplets and fomites through which virus can enter mostly into respiratory tract and cause the disease¹⁶. A study suggested the incubation period of covid-19 is 2-14 days¹⁷.

Signs and symptoms of covid-19 range from asymptomatic patient to severe disease and death. Respiratory tract involvement is common according to center for disease control the symptoms of covid-19 can be cough, fever, shortness of breath, persistent pain or pressure in chest and a new onset confusion, in signs bluish lips or face maybe seen.

According to world health organization covid-19 situation report-46 infections from covid-19 are 80% mild or asymptomatic, 15% are severe infection requiring oxygen and 5% are critical

infection requiring ventilation. The same report also says that older age and underlying conditions increase the risk for severe infection and crude mortality ratio of covid-19 until now is between 3-4%.

PREVENTION AND TREATMENT

As we know until now that the disease can be spread by droplets, contact and fomites, World health organization suggest preventive measures which include wearing a mask, hand hygiene(washing hands frequently, avoidance of handshake),maintaining social distance(3 feet from person coughing or sneezing),avoidance of touching nose,eyes and mouth, and maintaining respiratory hygien(coughing or sneezing into bent elbow or tissue).

Currently there are no vaccines or therapeutics available for covid-19. But according to world health organization there are a number of therapeutics currently in clinical trials in china and more than 20 vaccines are under development. One of the studies suggested chloroquine phosphate efficacy in treatment of covid-19¹⁷.

For the infected patient's world health organization (WHO) recommends interim guidance¹⁸.

CONCLUSION

COVID-19 is pandemic now. As till now no vaccines and specific treatment available for covid-19 and the number of deaths is in thousands, more and more drug trails should be carried out, and must to follow health authorities' guidelines regarding covid-19 prevention. Although the number of recovering patients are very high but strict prevention protocols should be followed because it is now a global health threat. Awareness regarding covid-19 should be encouraged.

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